

DEVELOPMENT OF AROMATIC DIAMIDES AS CROSS-LINKING AGENTS

FOR EPOXY RESINS

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The components of organic polymers used as matrices in composite structures must be safe to use, easy to process and produce plastics that are strong, ductile, and resistant to severe service environments. Diamides from aromatic dicarboxylic acids and aromatic primary amines have been developed as cross-linking agents for epoxy resins to meet these requirements. The diamide from phthalic anhydride (PA) and methylene dianiline (MDA) is described in detail. Several procedures for its preparation are compared and described. This cross-linking agent processed with a DGEBA epoxy resin produced materials with tensile strengths of 14000-15000 lb/in.², elongations of 6-10%, and ductile fracture. With a phenol novolac epoxy resin, strengths in excess of 15000 lb/in.² were achieved. Fracture surfaces of the materials have been examined in the electron microscope and the micromechanisms of fracture are described.

Introduction

The components of organic polymers used as matrices in composite structures must be safe to use, easy to process, and produce plastics that are strong, ductile, and resistant to severe service environments. Diamides from aromatic dicarboxylic acids and aromatic primary amines have been developed as cross-linking agents for epoxy resins to meet these requirements, Ref. 1.

The aromatic amines present processing difficulties because some are flakes or fine powders where the dust and vapour may be toxic, Ref. 2-3. Some have high melting points (above 80°C) and many, when mixed with epoxy resin, reach the "B stage" state rapidly. These difficulties can be minimized by the use of eutectic amine mixtures, small batch additions, and careful organization of process procedures.

The common anhydrides, phthalic anhydride (PA), methylenedimethylene-tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (NMA) or methyltetrahydrophthalic anhydride (MTHPA) also have toxic and irritating fumes. While NMA and MTHPA are liquids, PA is a white solid that fumes and sublimates during heating. It can be combined with other anhydrides to give a lower melting point than that of PA (130.8°C), but dust or fumes still present problems.

A search for solutions to these processing problems led to the development of the diamides at NAE, Ref. 1. These are made by combining the anhydrides with aromatic amines in the ratio of one to two leaving two reactive primary amine terminals and two active hydrogens in the amide sites as shown in equation 1. The diamides can also be made from the methyl ester of the aromatic acid as shown in equation 2.

Generally these diamides are reddish orange tacky solids at room temperature with low melting points (40-50°C), and with relatively low viscosities at higher temperatures. The freedom from dust reduced the toxicity factors. With experience it has been found that fuming and skin irritation were reduced to a greater extent than with amines or anhydrides, during processing. The time to reach "B stage" has in some cases been increased and in some decreased, but the viscosity when mixed with resins like EPON 828 is higher than with either the anhydrides or amines alone.

Because of difficulties that have been occasionally experienced with the technique presented in Ref. 1, further development in the preparation of these aromatic diamides was undertaken. This paper describes these developed techniques of preparation of several diamides. Data on cross-linking times, exothermic temperatures, tensile properties, and micro-mechanisms of fracture of materials produced from the reaction between the diamides and epoxy resins are included.

The materials used in the preparation of these diamides and their designations are given as are the diamides and their abbreviated codes.

Three epoxy resins were used in this development programme. Two of the resins were of the DGEBA family, CIBA 6004 and EPON 828, while the third was of the phenol novolac family DEN 431. CIBA 6004 and DEN 431 were selected because of low viscosity in each of the families. The equivalent weights are given in Table 1.

Table I. Stoichiometric Concentrations, phr

Ident.	Resin Eq. wt.	CLA	Eq. wt.	Cross-link Agent	
				6 A.H.*	4 A.H.*
CIBA6004	185	P	526	47	71
		M	556	50	75
		N	542	48.8	73
		V	544	49	73.5
		MDA	198	--	26.7
EPON828	190	P	526	46	69
		M	556	48.7	73
		N	542	47.5	71
		V	544	47.7	71.5
		MDA	198	--	26
DEN431	175	P	526	50	75
		M	556	53	79
		N	542	51.6	77
		V	544	51.8	77.7
		MDA	198	--	28.3

*A.H. is active hydrogen

Experimental Procedures

Preparation of the Diamides

Procedure 1

The diamides were prepared by heating a slight excess of the primary amine (MDA), to which had been added 0.1% benzyldimethylamine (BDMA), under a continuous flow of argon to 150°C. The anhydride was slowly added, to a final ratio of one molecular weight of anhydride to two molecular weights of amine while constantly stirring and maintaining the temperature at about 150°C. The light colour of the amine changed to a reddish colour and darkened. When some 25% of the anhydride had been added the mixture began to bubble and foam on each further addition and when the additions were completed the evolution of gases subsided after about 15 minutes. The temperature was held at 150°C for an additional 15 minutes and the material was set aside to cool.

The diamides V, N and M were made by this procedure. However, Pa required heating to 230°C before setting aside to cool.

Procedure 2

The diamide (Pe) formed from the reaction of the primary amine (MDA) and methyl ester of phthalic acid was prepared by heating two moles of the amines with one mole of the ester in a florence flask containing 0.25-1% catalyst such as BDMA, under a continuous flow of argon. Heating was carried out at a rate of 5 to 6°C per minute to 190°C and was maintained at that temperature for one hour. During the initial reaction methyl alcohol was evolved (Equation 2). This reduced the heating rate until the alcohol was substantially removed. The light fawn colour of the MDA changed to a dark reddish orange as the diamide developed. On completion of processing the transparent slightly viscous product was allowed to cool to room temperature.

Method for the Determination of Cross-Linking Time and Exothermic Temperature

An apparatus for determining cross-linking time and exothermic temperature is described in Ref. 4. It consists of an insulated flask with means of heating and cooling, a bottom reaction vessel, a top vessel, a thermocouple probe-stirrer, and a time temperature recording system. In a typical procedure the epoxy resin was placed in a reaction vessel and the cross-linking agents in the top vessel. When the temperature of the reactants had stabilized at the initiation temperature of 100°C the top vessel was pierced with probe-stirrer allowing the contents to drain into the reaction vessel. The reactants were stirred for three minutes. The recorder provided a continuous record of the time and temperature during the progress of the reaction.

The cross-linking time was arbitrarily defined as the time between the commencement of stirring and the point of maximum slope of the time-temperature trace.

The exothermic temperature was defined as the difference between the maximum temperature recorded and the initiation temperature.

Preparation of Plastic Sheets and Bars

All reactants, weighed at room temperature, were heated to 95°C (with stirring) to reduce the viscosity and gas bubbles, and poured into preheated

metal moulds for curing in an air circulating oven. After curing the 1/8 inch thick 6 in. x 3 in. cast sheets were allowed to cool before removal.

Determination of Deflection Temperature under Flexural Load

Rectangular bars of cast plastic 1/2" x 1/2" x 5" long were loaded in flexure to a fiber stress of 264 psi and tested in an oil bath as outlined in ASTM D648-72 "Deflection Temperature of Plastics under Flexural Load". The temperature at which the bar was deflected to 0.010 in. was taken as the Deflection Temperature (DT).

Determination of Tensile Properties

Strips of the cast plastic were cut on a high speed cutter to a shape that met ASTM D638-68 Type II. After determining the dimensions of the cross section, they were loaded in a testing machine with load elongation recorded on an x-y chart. An extensometer was used to measure elongation over a 1.0 cm gauge length when determining modulus values. The tensile modulus of elasticity was determined from the initial slope of the load-strain curve.

The type of failure as determined by the load elongation curve, was recorded. The assessment of type of failure was based on the following definitions:

- (i) Brittle: Failure occurred while load and elongation were increasing.
- (ii) Yield: Failure occurred while elongation was increasing and load was remaining constant.
- (iii) Ductile: Failure occurred while elongation was increasing and load was decreasing.

Experimental Results

Determination of Cross-Linking Time and Exothermic Temperature

In the development of materials and determination of processing schedules for reactive epoxide compositions it was necessary to know the exothermic temperature of the reaction, and the time to gel under known conditions. Figure 1 shows plots of the exothermic temperatures and concentrations of the cross-linking agents in the reactive compositions consisting of MDA, Pa, Pe, M, N and V using the DGEBA resin EPON 828. The smooth curve for MDA shows a maximum exothermic temperature of 162°C at approximately 30 phr (parts per hundred of resin). This is characteristic of a simple reaction where there are four reactive hydrogens.

The curves for Pa, Pe, M, N and V are characteristics of more complex reactions and may be expected when there are at least six reactive hydrogens - four on the two primary amine groups and one for each amide linkage. V shows a maximum exothermic temperature of 141°C, M a maximum of 138°C, N a maximum of 137°C, Pa a maximum of 133°C, and Pe a maximum of 128°C. These maxima are useful in the determination of the practical concentration of cross-linking agent to be used in the processing of these materials. For convenience the stoichiometric concentration of the resins and cross-linking agents are listed in Table I.

Fig.1 Exothermic Temperature vs Concentration for EPON 828 Cross-Linked with Various Diamides

Fig.2 Cross-Linking Time vs Concentration for EPON 828 with Various Diamides

Figure 2 shows the curves for cross-linking time as concentration of cross-linking agent in EPON 828 at the initiation temperature of 100°C. All of the diamides show well defined times of cross-linking which can be related to working times in factory processing. However, the rate of increase of viscosity of the reactants must also be considered when establishing working times. If the maximum exothermic temperature is selected to establish the final concentration of cross-linking agent, then Pe, N and Pa have cross-linking times of about 10.5 minutes, MDA a time of 9 minutes, M 7 minutes and V has the shortest time of 4.5 minutes.

Figure 3 shows the exothermic temperature curves for the diamide Pe of five different compositions, (Table II). The curve for MDA is retained for comparison.

Pe	MDA	DMPA	TEA.HCl*
P ₁	99gm	35.7gm	0.25gm
P ₂	99	44	0.25
P ₃	99	48.5	0.25
P ₄	99	53.5	0.25
P ₅	99	53.5	1.00

*Triethylamine Hydrochloride

These curves were helpful in the development of a Pe cross-linking agent particularly when there was correlation with the observed mechanical properties.

Figure 4 shows the curves for cross-linking time for the Pe series (Table II). Cross-linking times for P₁ and P₂ remain at 10.5 minutes at 58 phr, while cross-linking times for P₃, P₄ and P₅ become progressively longer. This indicates a potential for longer working times for P₃, P₄ and P₅, and a higher diamide content.

Fig.3 Exothermic Temperature vs Concentration for EPON 828 with Pe of Different Compositions

Fig.4 Cross-Linking Time vs Concentration for EPON 828 with Pe of Different Compositions

Table III. Deflection Temperatures under Flexural Load

Diamide	phr	Cure			Deflection Temperature °C			
		Initial °C	Intermed. Hr.	Final °C	EPON828	DEN431		
Pa	50	80	2	100	4	160 8	134	150
Pe	50	80	2	100	4	160 8	110	122
Pe*	50	80	2	100	4	160 8	-	128
Pe	50	80	2	100	4	180 8	113	-
V	50	80	2	100	4	160 8	134	141
N	55	80	2	-	-	160 8	-	143
N	55	80	4	-	-	200 8	-	150
N	55	80	4	-	-	240 8	-	153
N	50	80	2	100	4	160 8	143	-
M	55	80	2	-	-	160 8	-	146
M	50	80	2	100	4	160 8	147	146
MDA	26	80	2	100	4	160 8	166	-

Note: (1) Pa from anhydride, Pe from ester
 (2) *prepared at 230°C.

Determination of Deflection Temperatures (DT) Under Flexural Load

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The deflection temperatures were determined under flexural load to provide an indication of the behaviour of the plastic at elevated temperature and to provide a basis for comparing the thermal performance of the plastics made with different cross-linking agents.

Table III compares the results of deflection temperature tests with a DGEBA resin EPON828, and a phenol novolac resin DEN431. The phenol novolac resin exhibits DT's which are higher than EPON828 when cross-linked with Pa, Pe and V. However, the DT's for the two resins are the same when cross-linked with N and M. Generally higher final cure temperatures raise the DT until a limit is reached. This limit is illustrated by the diamide N where a final cure temperature of 240°C raised the DT to 153°C from 150°C for a cure temperature of 200°C.

It should be noted that the diamide Pe made from the ester of phthalic acid has different thermal properties from that made with phthalic anhydride, suggesting different compositions or structures. More investigation is required in this area to determine the reason for this difference.

Tensile Properties of Diamides and Epoxy Resins

The epoxy resins were cross-linked with the diamides and MDA. Bubbles were observed in several cured sheets. Most likely they were entrapped air. Processing procedures using solvents would practically eliminate viscosity problems but solvent free materials were required in this assessment.

Table V. Tensile Strength for Various Diamides and Concentrations: Cure 80°C for 4 hr. and 160°C for 8 hr.: Resin CIBA6004

CLA	Conc. phr	Tensile Strength psi	Type of Failure
Pa	40	15100	ductile
	45	10200	brittle
	50	14500	yield
	55	14700	yield
	65	15100	ductile
M	70	14000	brittle
	45	14500	ductile
	50	13600	ductile
	55	13700	ductile
	60	13700	ductile
	65	13700	ductile
	70	10800	brittle
N	40	13500	brittle
	45	14400	ductile
	50	14100	ductile
V	55	14100	ductile
	65	14100	ductile
	70	14300	ductile
	40	14900	ductile
	45	13500	brittle
	50	14000	ductile
	55	14000	ductile
MDA*	65	14200	ductile
	70	11800	brittle
	24	14000	yield
	27	11400	brittle
	30	12200	ductile
	33	12200	ductile
	39	13900	ductile
	42	14300	ductile
	47	14400	brittle

* Cured at 180°C

Table IV. Tensile Strength for Various Diamides, Resins and Final Cure Temperatures: Concentration 55 phr

Resin	CLA	Final Cure Temp. °C	Tensile Strength psi	Type of Failure
EPON828	Pa	160°	14700	ductile
		160°	14500	ductile
		180°	11300	brittle
	M	160°	13900	ductile
		180°	13900	ductile
		220°	14700	ductile
		240°	14800	ductile
	N	260°	15000	brittle
		160°	14400	ductile
		220°	14900	ductile
DEN431	M	240°	14500	brittle
		160°	15200	ductile
CIBA6004	Pa	220°	15200	yield
		160°	14400	yield
	M	180°	14900	ductile
		200°	15000	ductile
		220°	11500	brittle
	N	160°	13700	ductile
		180°	13200	ductile
		200°	14000	ductile
		160°	14100	ductile
		180°	14100	ductile
V	200°	13600	brittle	
	160°	14000	ductile	
	180°	14300	ductile	
		200°	14600	ductile

The tensile strength data presented in Table IV indicate strength dependency on the resins and the final cure temperature. Tensile strengths ranged from 13000 - 15000 lb/in². Generally, the phenol novolac resin exhibited the highest strength with EPON828 next and CIBA6004 the lowest. It should be kept in mind that all combinations were 55 phr. All strengths increased with increased final cure temperatures.

The tensile strength data presented in Table V for CIBA6004 resin indicate apparent strength dependency on concentration of cross-linking agent. Generally, ductile failures occurred over a range of concentration starting below the 6 active hydrogen values of Table I and continuing almost to the concentration of the 4 active hydrogen values.

Table VI shows tensile strength for the P₁ to P₅ series correspond to those shown in Figure 3, at 55 phr with EPON828. P₆ has been added to illustrate the effect on tensile strength of high catalyst concentration in the preparation of the cross-linking agent Pe.

Table VI. Tensile Strength of Pe and EPON828 Cured at 160°C for Various Ester and Catalyst Concentrations of Pe

Pe	MDA gm	DMPA gm	Cat. gm TEA.HCl	Pe Conc. phr	Tensile Strength psi	Type of Failure
P-1	99	35.7	.25	55	14100	ductile
P-2	99	44.0	.25	55	14500	ductile
P-3	99	48.5	.25	55	14500	ductile
P-4	99	53.5	.25	55	14500	ductile
P-5	99	53.5	1.0	55	14800	ductile
P-6	99	47.0	4.0*	55	15200	ductile

*BDMA Catalyst

The tensile modulus data presented in Table VII indicate that the diamides cured with EPON828 have modulus values ranging from 3×10^5 psi to 4×10^5 psi. The values for Pe were the highest while M and V were the lowest.

Table VII. Tensile Property Values for Various Diamides with EPON828: Cure 80°C for 4 hr. and 160°C for 8 hr.

Resin	Diamide	Conc. phr	Tensile	
			Strength psi	Modulus psi
EPON828	Pe	40	14700	3.8×10^5
		50	14400	3.6×10^5
	M	45	14100	3.5×10^5
		50	11900	3.6×10^5
	N	45	13800	2.8×10^5
		50	13800	3.1×10^5
	V	45	13700	3.1×10^5
		50	13800	3.1×10^5

Fig. 5 Typical Stress-Strain Curve

Micro-Mechanisms of Fracture

Crack Initiation

Fractographic examination of the tensile specimens of this material in the electron microscope has provided information concerning the initiation of the cracks leading to failure of the specimens, as well as some interesting observations regarding the micro-mechanisms of crack propagation.

The crack initiators invariably consisted of discontinuities or flaws within the body of the material or on the surface of the specimens. Those flaws found within the specimens appeared to be material inhomogenities, while those on the surface could be related to minute surface discontinuities formed during specimen preparation.

The crack initiating flaws may take the form of:

- (1) Spherical voids, probably formed by entrapped air, or by gas bubbles formed during chemical reactions within the polymer during the thermosetting process, Fig. 6.
- (2) Discontinuities near the surface of the specimens, Figs. 7 and 8.
- (3) Small islands or masses of material within the specimen that appear to have discrete boundaries separating them from the main body of the matrix material, Figs. 9 and 10.

Fig. 6 Fracture initiated at a spherical void (SEM).

Fig. 8 Fracture initiated at a sub-surface flaw (SEM).

Fig. 7 Fracture initiated at surface flaws (SEM).

Fig. 9 Fracture initiated at an internal flaw (SEM).

Crack Propagation

The crack nucleus, which may be considered to be the stress concentration that initiates the crack, is generally surrounded by a relatively smooth, featureless mirror-like region on the fracture surface, when viewed at relatively low magnification, Fig. 6. At somewhat higher magnifications, however, as shown in Fig. 10, this mirror-like region is actually seen to consist of multitudes of minute parabolas, all pointing towards the crack-initiating defect. It is the formation of these parabolas during the fracture process that provides an interesting insight into the fracture mechanisms of these and related polymers.

Formation of Parabolic Features

The parabolic fracture features become more pronounced as the crack front recedes from the origin (Fig. 11). It would appear that each "parabola" is in effect a separate fracture surface entity, with its own crack-initiating nucleus from which lines of fracture appear to radiate in all directions. This can be observed quite clearly in Figures 12 and 13, where small, apparently spherical defects, some 0.15 micron in diameter appear to be the nuclei of the fracture within the confines of the

Fig. 10 Fracture initiated at an internal flaw. Note parabolas.

Fig. 11 Parabolic fracture surface features.

Fig. 12 Parabolic domains originating from minute defects (TEM). Plastic-carbon replica. x1,200

Fig. 13 Spherical defect initiating parabolic fracture domain (TEM). Plastic-carbon replica. x6,500

parabolas. Speculation as to the precise micro-mechanism of formation of the parabolic entities led to the conclusion that the location of the nuclei of fracture in the parabolas must correspond closely to their focii, and that fracture initiating from any given focal point must begin before the crack front from the preceding parabola has arrived at the succeeding focus.

Thus if it is assumed that over the fracture surface area of some 0.003 mm² illustrated in Fig. 14, the velocities of the crack fronts are reasonably constant and equal in the two parabolic domains, as they radiate in all directions from the focii of the two parabolas, the crack originating from the focus of parabola B (Fig. 15) must have been initiated at the instant that the crack front that was initiated from the focus of parabola A had reached arc C. The distance between focus B and arc C would be approximately equal to twice the focal distance of parabola B.

Fig. 14 Two parabolic fracture domains (SEM).

Fig. 15 Diagram showing proposed fracture sequence in two parabolic domains.

Further to verify the plausibility of this proposed fracture micro-mechanism, and the assumption of approximately equal crack growth rates in both parabolic domains, the distances BD and CD (D being any point on parabola B) were measured and found to be approximately equal. This would tend to substantiate the hypothesis that the crack emanating from focus B was initiated at the instant that the crack originating from focus A had reached arc C.

Figure 16, illustrating the complete fracture surface of one of the tensile specimens of this material, shows that as the crack front recedes from the origin, the fracture surface topography becomes progressively rougher in texture. At greater magnification (X75) this topography

appears to possess a granular or cellular structure, Fig. 17. At a magnification of X200 (Fig. 18), however the parabolic structure of the fracture surface once more becomes clearly visible, and the relatively rough texture of the fracture topography can be attributed to the fact that the parabolic fracture domains have been initiated at different levels along the tensile axis of the test specimens. It was also established that even at these remote distances (3 to 4 mm) from the crack nucleus, the orientation of the parabolas remained such that they "pointed" towards the initial origin of fracture.

Fig. 16 Fracture surface of tensile specimen (SEM)

Fig. 18 Parabolic fracture domains formed at various levels contribute to the rough texture of the fracture surfaces (SEM).

Fig. 17 Cellular texture of rough fracture surface areas (SEM).

Conclusions

Diamide cross-linking agents for use with epoxy resins have been made successfully from methylene dianiline and four common carboxylic acid anhydride compounds, and a methyl ester of phthalic anhydride. The plastics made from these various compositions have exhibited tensile strengths ranging from 13000 to 15000 lb/in², elongations up to 10%, and ductile fractures over a range of concentrations of the diamide cross-linking agents. The deflection temperatures for these materials ranged from 110°C to 150°C.

Fractographic examination of these materials has provided information concerning the initiation and propagation of cracks leading to failure, and demonstrating that the micro-mechanism of fracture involves the initiation of multiple minute cracks in the form of parabolic domains. Direct correlation between fractographic features and types of failure have not been established to date.

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